

STRATEGIC ADAPTABILITY FOR MARKET LEADERSHIP IN INDONESIA'S BABY CARE INDUSTRY USING SCENARIO PLANNING

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Abstract

The Indonesian baby care industry faces uncertainty driven by economic volatility, rapid digital transformation, changing consumer preferences, demand for product safety, and intensifying competition. These conditions challenge companies to maintain long-term market leadership using strategic planning approaches. This study aims to develop strategic adaptability for sustaining market leadership in Indonesia's baby care industry through a scenario planning approach. This research conducted a qualitative method using semi-structured interviews with internal and external industry experts. Interview findings were formulated into driving forces, followed by prioritization assessment to identify the two major critical uncertainties shaping the future industry environment. Then, the four plausible future scenarios were developed, namely The Battle Arena, The Golden Age, The Dark Times and The Old Guard, along with early warning signals to anticipate changes in macroeconomic and industry conditions. The findings indicate that strategic adaptability is essential for sustaining market leadership under uncertain market condition. The study further integrated scenario planning with an evaluation of current strategy to identify strategic gaps under future scenario. A TOWS matrix was subsequently formulated. It resulted in several strategic recommendation pillars with different adaptive adjustments across scenarios, followed by implementation roadmap for the next five years.

Keywords: Strategic Adaptability, Scenario Planning, Baby Care Industry, Market Leadership, PESTLE analysis, Porter's Five Forces analysis, TOWS matrix

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's baby care industry continues to demonstrate strong market potential. According to Euromonitor (2025), the Indonesia baby and child toiletries market recorded a CAGR of 7,4% during 2019-2024. This numbers indicate the growing demand for baby care products in Indonesia. However, despite the market potential, the industry is facing future uncertainty conditions driven by macroeconomic pressures, evolving consumer preferences, digital disruptions, rising demand for product safety and intensifying competition. As local brand company, PT Momentum Pacific Tbk's brand (the name is made vague due to confidentiality) has been produced various fast-moving consumer goods product, especially baby and kids care products, namely BabyM, for more than 40 years. BabyM was selected as the object of this study because it represents one of the leading local brands in Indonesia's baby care industry with strong brand trust, extensive distribution networks, and long-established consumer loyalty.

Retail Audit Nielsen Data (2025) of baby telon oil, year-to-date June 2025, BabyM has dominated baby telon oil market for more than 70% in volume contribution. Along with its leading in baby telon oil, BabyM also dominated the market for 40,9% in volume contribution of market baby powder (Nielsen, 2025). Unlike many emerging brands that mainly rely on digital penetration or niche positioning, BabyM combines product innovation, affordable pricing and widely distribution network across distribution channel in Indonesia. These conditions make BabyM a relevant and important case for examining how strategic adaptability and Scenario Planning can support long-term market leadership under uncertain future business environments. This study examines the relationship between business uncertainty, strategic adaptability, and market leadership within Indonesia's baby care industry. According to the internal report in year-to-date June 2025, sales trend of BabyM experienced a significant declining performance of -7,6% compared to last year with only 80% achievement of sales target. For several paste years, BabyM has maintained its position as market leader, they lack to adapt flexibility and proactive risk anticipation. For demand

and forecasting, BabyM still used traditional planning models which are usually forecast-based and linear. Research conducted to identify the observable attitude of them relies on fixed projections and stable assumptions, rather than applying an adaptive scenario planning analysis. On the other hand, the increasing uncertainty related to economic conditions, digital acceleration, consumer behavior shifts, and competitive intensity may influence the company's ability to sustain long-term competitiveness. Scenario Planning is used as a strategic foresight approach to explore multiple plausible future environments and support adaptive strategic decision-making. In addition, the identification of early warning signals is expected to strengthen strategic monitoring capability and improve organizational responsiveness toward future market changes.

The goal of this study is to formulate the strategic recommendations that can strengthen BabyM's market leadership and improve its long-term competitiveness in Indonesia's baby care industry over the next five years. Practically, this study is expected to support companies in improving strategic adaptability, organizational agility, and long-term market leadership readiness amid changing market dynamics. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to identify critical business uncertainties affecting BabyM's market leadership, develop plausible future scenarios, identify early warning signal and formulate adaptive strategic recommendations to strengthen long-term competitiveness under uncertain future conditions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scenario Planning

Dean (2019) stated that there are 5 stages to construct a scenario planning process. The process of Scenario Planning will involve key stakeholders of the organization to provide key information and include the following steps: orientation, exploration, scenario creation, implication & options and integration into the current management process.

PESTLE Analysis

PESTLE model is a framework that categorizes and analyzes comprehensive external factors that are Economic, Political, Socio-cultural, Technological, Ecological and Legal that affect a company. These factors can create both opportunities and threats for the firm.

Porter's Five Forces

According to Michael E. Porter (2008), Porter's Five Forces framework several factors such as rivalry among existing firms, threats of new entrants, power of buyers, power of suppliers and threats of substitutes can help to determine and company's opportunities and risks surrounding in baby care market industry.

SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis is a framework used for analyzing the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats of a company. The goal of SWOT analysis is to match the company's strengths with the opportunities of the company while eliminating the weaknesses and minimizing the threats (Karppi, et al, 2001).

TOWS Analysis

The TOWS Analysis is a strategic management tool developed by Heinz Wehrich (1982) and later expanded by Wheelen & Hunger (2012) as a practical extension of the SWOT Analysis framework. The SWOT Analysis often focuses on identifying internal and external factors, while the TOWS Matrix takes the next step by systematically these factors to generate strategic alternatives.

METHOD

Data Collection Method

Data collection is the process of gathering and examining data using a specific method. The objective is to ensure the data used in the research are suitable, sufficient and measurable to perform the data analysis process and achieve the research objectives (Syed & Qadri, 2021). In this study, there are two types of data which author need to be collected, primary data and secondary data.

Primary Data: Semi-Structured Method

The author conducted with qualitative research to gather the data. The qualitative research is implemented by semi-structured interviews with purposive sampling approach to gain more insights about internal and external

situations, focusing in the business issue. The qualitative data from semi-structured interview is analyzed using the manual data coding which essential activity within the qualitative research process. Following the profile of participants:

Table 1. Interviewee's profile

Initial	Background	Experience
TY	Brand Development & Product Innovation	>15 years
RA	Brand Creative Content & Communication	>10 years
IT	Brand Consume Marketing	>10 years
QE	Corporate Sales & Trade Marketing	>10 years
AL	Brand Media Investment	>10 years
DH	Product Development & Innovation	>5 years

Secondary Data: Literature Review

The secondary data is gathered by analyzing the exist variety of sources the exist variety of sources including academic journals, paper, other literature review, quarterly macroeconomics reports, brand health tracking databases and previous study of consumer behavior and brand perception.

Data Analysis Method

The first step involves designing a comprehensive interview questions that aligns with the research objectives and constructs investigation about current business issues which affected the business ups or down sales performance and the relationship of political, economic, socio-cultural, technology, environment and legal situation to future.

Thematic Analysis for Data Processing

Naeem et al (2023) mention the thematic analysis process by analyzing the transcripts to find the interesting findings as its keywords. The keywords then will be marked systematically and submitted as code. The codes will be grouped into potential themes which will be described clearly so that it is understood that each of theme reflected its own essence. Then, the codes will be grouped as clusters, which will become the driving factors in the business contextual environment.

External Factor Analysis: PESTLE Analysis & Porter's Five Forces

The external environment analysis is analyzed using PESTLE Analysis and Porter's Five Forces to evaluate macroenvironmental factors, market competition, and industry dynamics that affecting BabyM's business performance. In this study, the PESTLE Analysis is used as framework to categorize the external factors from area of Economic, Political, Socio-Cultural, Technological, Environmental and Legal aspects which is affected BabyM's performance. Meanwhile, Porter's Five Forces framework is used to identify baby care market industry and its competitiveness.

Internal Factor Analysis: SW from SWOT

The internal analysis is analyzed using SWOT Analysis and synthesized into a SWOT Matrix. To complement the external analysis previously, this research applies the SWOT framework to evaluate BabyM's internal environment, focusing on evolving consumer behavior, market uncertainty, and its readiness to respond to increasing competition. Insight derived from internal stakeholder with semi-structured interview, supported by relevant literature.

Scenario Planning Analysis

Garvin & Levesque (2006) highlighted the five steps of Scenario Planning, including Orientation, Exploration, Scenario Creation, Implications, and Integration. This study further exercises the adaptative strategic adjustment process and implementation roadmap.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thematic Data Analysis

The external factors will describe the current conditions of Indonesia's baby care. The codebook was developed through an iterative process, starting with the identification of initial codes from the interview transcripts. Then, the codes were organized and clearly defined based on patterns coming up in the data and supported by relevant literature. Each code also including a definition and application criteria to ensure consistency and transparency in the analysis (DeCuir-Gunby, 2011). industry.

PESTLE Analysis

The following details of the PESTLE analysis will be explained below:

- **Political:** The global geopolitical instability has bigger effect on the logistic and supply chain environment in Indonesia, especially for FMCG industries that rely on imported raw materials and packaging components. Disruptions in global trade flows and geopolitical tensions have led to delivery times longer and increased uncertainty in materials availability. According to BabyM's internal data (2026), there is the rise in plastic resin prices which gave impact to the packaging cost for 30-35% higher than before the global geopolitical instability rises.
- **Economic:** Economic condition is one of the most important factors of companies' performance in baby care industry. Indonesia's GDP growth from 2022 to 2025 has remained resilient, consistently growing around 5% annually, according to reports from Bank Indonesia and Statistic Indonesia (BPS). However, the personal care and other services sector experienced a significant inflationary pressure in Indonesia during December 2025 with 6,5% higher than previous year. The declining purchasing power of Indonesian consumers, as highlighted in the interviews, has led to increased price sensitivity.
- **Social:** Social dynamics are evolving shaping the demand for baby care products significantly. One of the most critical structural challenges is the declining birth rate, Indonesia birth rate for 2025 is 2,19%, a 0,73% decline from 2024 (Statista, 2025). Whereas, consumers are becoming more informed and selective in their purchasing decisions.
- **Technology:** The social commerce market in Indonesia is expected to grow by 17,1% on annual basis to reach USD 5,25 billion by 2025. With a historic CAGR of 24,9% from 2021-2024., the industry anticipates continued expansion, projecting a CAGR of 10,4% from 2025 to 2030 with market size approximately USD 8,62 billion by 2030 (yahoo! finance, 2026). This trend indicates the increasing role of digital and interactive commerce channels in shaping the consumer purchasing behavior. This condition strengthens the role of digital platforms, influencer marketing, and online communities in influencing consumer purchasing behaviour, especially among younger and digitally connected parents
- **Legal:** BPOM Indonesia has made all products must pass through the strict product safety regulation and certification requirements. While this can boost consumer confidence in buying some products, it also increases compliance costs and time-to-market for companies.
- **Environmental factor:** As mentioned in the interview, there is a growing demand for eco-friendly packaging, particularly among consumer who are more aware and environmental conscious. The eco-friendly packaging trend forces companies to innovate in packaging design and material selection.

Porter's Five Forces Analysis

While the PESTLE analysis provides macro-level understanding of external forces that may affect to the baby care industry, it doesn't fully capture the competitive dynamic within the market. Through the Porter's Five Forces framework, it is used to analyze the structure and intensity of competition in Indonesia's baby care industry. The results as in table 1.

Table 1. Porter’s Five Forces (author analysis)

Porter’s Five Forces	Code	Level of Impact
Threats of New Entrants	Easy entry	High
	Strong brand trust requirement	
	Distribution barrier (offline)	
	High investment (ATL/BTL)	
Bargaining Power of Buyers	Price sensitivity	High
	Price comparison behavior	
	Smart & informed consumers	
	Switching behavior	
Bargaining Power of Suppliers	High dependency on suppliers	High
	Impact on production & launch	
	Rising raw material costs	
	Lead time uncertainty	
Threats of Substitute	Availability of alternative brands	Moderate-High
	Product switching	
	Functional similarity	
Competitive Rivalry	Intense competition	Very High
	Price war	
	Many competitors	
	Digital competition	
	Strong existing brands	

SWOT Matrix

The internal stakeholder points out that BabyM has strengths in its position of Indonesia’s market leader and internal capabilities. As mentioned previously, the internal strengths of BabyM can help brand to maintain competitiveness and consumer’s loyalty in Indonesia’s baby care market. However, the internal weaknesses suggest areas may hinder the brand’s ability to respond effectively and quickly to external challenges. By integrating internal factors with the previously external opportunities and threats, a comprehensive SWOT matrix is developed as seen in Figure 2.

<p>STRENGTH:</p> <p>S1: Market Leadership S2: Strong Brand Trust S3: Value for Money Positioning S4: Wide Distribution Network</p>	<p>WEAKNESS:</p> <p>W1: Digital Capability Limitation W2: Supply Chain Constraint W3: Price Competition Pressure W4: Internal Coordination Complexity</p>
<p>OPPORTUNITY</p> <p>O1: Growth of Digital and Social Commerce O2: Increasing Consumer Awareness on Product Quality and Safety O3: Strong Brand Trust as a Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>THREAT:</p> <p>T1: Declining Birth Rate T2: Increasing Price Sensitivity and Declining Purchasing Power T3: Intense Competition and Price Wars T4: Rising Raw Material and Packaging Costs</p>

Figure 2. SWOT Analysis (author analysis)

Scenario Planning Creations

Stage 1: Orientation

To understand future uncertainties, this research focuses on BabyM’s long term strategic for its competitive positioning. The selected time horizon for the scenarios is 2026 – 2031. The key focal issue addressed in this study is how can BabyM sustain and strengthen its competitive advantage in Indonesia’s baby care market while facing intensifying competition, dynamic consumer expectations and regulatory uncertainties in the next five years.

Stage 2: Exploration

Stage 2 consists of a systematic examination of the external environment to identify trends and forces shaping the future of Indonesian baby care industry. This analysis applies the PESTLE framework, Porter’s Five Forces and SW from SWOT analysis to identify key drivers that may influence BabyM’s position over the next five years. Summary of Driving Forces of Baby Care Industry in Indonesia in Table 2.

Stage 3: Scenario and Narrative Creations

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The third stage of scenario planning aims to identify the critical uncertainties that shape the future environment of the Indonesian baby care industry and determine the strategic axes for scenario construction. Participants from internal stakeholders were asked to rate each potential driving factor using scale 1= Low; 2 = Medium; 3 = High. The summary of value of impact and uncertainty and normalize value shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Summary of Driving Forces (author analysis)

Driving Forces	Explanation
Economic Pressure & Purchasing Power	As the interview and literature findings, economic pressures have made declining purchasing power, increasing price sensitivity, and shifting spending priorities.
Demographic & Social Changes	Changes in demographic structure in terms of declining birth rates which is directly impact the size of the baby care market. In addition, parenting behavior shift and increasing consumer awareness regarding product safety and quality also changed consumer's purchasing decision.
Digital Transformation & Market Access	The rapid growth of digital platforms has transformed how consumers access and evaluate baby care products through social commerce and e-commerce.
Industry Competition & Market Saturation	The baby care industry in Indonesia is characterized by intense competition, with the presence of both established and emerged brands.
Cost Structure & Supply Chain Dynamics	In price-sensitive market condition, the rising costs of raw materials and packaging could affect product prices, availability, and profit margins to the companies.
Sustainability & Environmental Pressure	Companies are using more eco-friendly packaging because people are becoming more aware of environmental issues.

Table 3. Summary of Value of Impact and Uncertainty and Normalize Value (author's analysis)

Driving Forces	Impact	Uncertainty	Driving Forces	Impact	Uncertainty
Economic Pressure & Purchasing Power	18	18	Economic Pressure & Purchasing Power	1,000	1,000
Demographic & Social Changes	9	12	Demographic & Social Changes	0,182	0,455
Digital Transformation & Market Access	14	17	Digital Transformation & Market Access	0,636	0,909
Industry Competition & Market Saturation	16	15	Industry Competition & Market Saturation	0,818	0,727
Cost Structure & Supply Chain Dynamics	17	16	Cost Structure & Supply Chain Dynamics	0,909	0,818
Sustainability & Environmental Pressure	10	7	Sustainability & Environmental Pressure	0,273	0,000

Figure 3. Uncertainty Matrix (author's analysis)

From the uncertainty matrix the critical uncertainties are Economic Conditions and Digital Transformation. Hence, the Scenario Planning of Indonesia's baby care industry as follows:

Figure 4. Scenario Planning (author's analysis)

Scenario Narratives

Scenario A: The Battle Arena

Jakarta Post, 2031: “Baby Care Brands Fight for Consumer Attention Amid Economic Pressure”. Indonesia's baby care industry enters an era of intense digital competition, while the economic pressure continues to challenge consumer purchasing power. Although Indonesia's digital economy and social commerce market continue to expand more rapid, inflationary pressure and rising living costs force consumers to become more selective and price-sensitive in their purchasing decisions. Consumers often compare products across digital platforms, more into prioritize promotions and discounts, and has lower brand loyalty due to many available product alternatives.

Scenario B: The Golden Age

Jakarta Post, 2031: “Indonesia's Baby Care Industry Enters a New Era of Smart Digital Growth”. Indonesia's baby care industry experiences strong economic growth and accelerated digital transformation, leading to reshape consumer behaviour across the country. Although the inflationary pressure remains present, Indonesia maintains relatively stable of GDP growth above 5%, while inflation gradually improved and more manageable compared to previous years. As the economic condition improve, consumers regain purchasing confidence and become more willing to spend their money for baby care products that offer quality, safety and still value for money.

Scenario C

Jakarta Post 2031: “Economic Pressure and Weak Consumer Demand Slow Indonesia's Baby Care Industry”. Indonesia's baby care industry face prolonged economic pressure, inflation remains high and consumer

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purchasing power continues to decline. Consumers force to become more cautious in their spending behaviour due to rising living costs and unstable economic conditions. Although e-commerce and social media platforms still available, the digital purchasing only increases in major urban areas. Digital transformation has a slower pace, with limited online market access and expansion. Consumers depend more on conventional purchasing habits in traditional market and offline channels.

Scenario D: The Old Guard

Jakarta, Post 2031: "Traditional Retail Channels Continue to Dominate Indonesia's Baby Care Market".

Indonesia's baby care industry continues to grow as economic conditions gradually improve, consumer purchasing power remains relatively stable and inflation becomes more manageable. The middle-income consumers regain spending confidence for essential baby care products. On the other hand, digital transformation develops at a slower pace compared to expectations. Consumers still prefer offline shopping experiences and buy baby care products on conventional retail channels. In addition, they rely more on word of mouth recommendation and direct explanations from sales promoters rather than digital reviews and influencer-driven content.

Early Warning Signals

Early warning signals are indicators used to monitor which future scenario is becoming more likely to occur. These indicators help BabyM anticipate market shifts and prepare strategic responses according to the scenario conditions. In this study, the early warning signals are identified based on changes in macroeconomic conditions, consumer purchasing behavior, and digital transformation trends in Indonesia's baby care industry.

Table 5. Early Warning Signals (author's analysis)

Aspect	Measure	Signals			
		Scenario A: The Battle Arena	Scenario B: The Golden Age	Scenario C: The Dark Times	Scenario D: The Old Guard
Economic	Indonesia GDP Growth	GDP remains stable around 5% but with inflation pressures	GDP growth remains above 5% annually	GDP growth slows below 5%	GDP growth remains relatively stable
	Household Consumption	Weakens	Continues growing	Declining household spending and reduced non-essential purchases	Stable spending on essential baby care products
	Consumer Confidence Index	Weakens	Optimistic	Declines significantly	Relatively stable
	Inflation Rate	Inflation remains above 5%	Inflation stabilizes below 3 - 4%	Inflation remains high above 5%	Inflation becomes more manageable
Consumer	Consumer Purchasing Behaviour	Consumers prioritize promotions and discounts	Consumers willing to spend more on trusted quality products	Consumers focus only on affordable essential products	Consumers maintain conventional purchasing habits
	Basket Size	Decreasing basket size and shift toward smaller packs	Increasing basket size and larger pack purchases	Decreasing basket size and delayed purchasing	Stable basket size in offline retail channels
Technology	Social Commerce Market Growth	Exceeds projected CAGR of 10,4%	Exceeds projected CAGR of 10,4%	Slows growth remains below projected CAGR of 10,4%	Slows below projected CAGR of 10,4%

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	E-commerce Penetration	Digital commerce and live shopping	Online channels contribute heavily to baby care sales	Limited online market channels expansion	Offline channels still dominant
	AI-driven Marketing Adoption	Aggressive AI-driven advertising and targeting competition	Increasing adoption of AI personalization	Low adoption of AI-driven marketing	Limited AI and omnichannel integration
Market	Premium Baby Care Demand	Consumers seek to affordable products with quality preference	Increasing willingness to pay for trusted quality and product performance	Declining demand for premium products	Moderate demand for trusted and affordable products
	Digital Engagement	High engagement driven by promotions, KOLs, and affiliate marketing	Increasing parenting community and influence engagement.	Limited digital engagement and reliance on traditional channels	Lower digital engagement and heavily dependence on offline interaction

Strategic Recommendation

Based on the TOWS matrix analysis across all scenarios, several strategic alternatives are identified to address future market uncertainty in Indonesia’s baby care industry. Several recurring themes consistently emerge across the scenarios. Therefore, author synthesizes the strategic alternatives into broadened strategic recommendation pillars that are considered more robust and relevant to support BabyM’s competitiveness in long-term under multiple future conditions. Following the strategic recommendation pillars: Consumer Engagement, Product Innovation, Operational Supply Chain, Brand Positioning dan Organizational Capability. The adjustment strategic recommendation based on each scenario can be seen in Table 6. Therefore, Figure 5 below illustrates the adaptive strategic adjustment process for BabyM in responding to future scenario shifts and environmental uncertainty.

Figure 5. Strategic Adjustment Process (author’s analysis)

Table 6. Adjustment Strategic Recommendation

Strategic Pillars	The Battle Arena	The Golden Age	The Dark Times	The Old Guard
Consumer Engagement	Strengthen live commerce and consumer retention program	Expand omnichannel engagement and parenting community activation	Maintain consumer reassurance through accessible retail communication	Focus on offline activation, retail engagement, and in-store consumer education
Product innovation	Develop relevant and affordable innovation	Develop science-based baby care innovation	Prioritize core and high-demand product categories with affordable product offerings	Focus on practical and essential baby care innovation
Operational and Supply Chain	Improve operational efficiency, inventory optimization, and supply responsiveness	Strengthen omnichannel inventory responsiveness and supply flexibility	Focus on operational efficiency, cost control, and core product availability	Strengthen retail coordination and traditional trade product availability
Brand Positioning	Reinforce value for money positioning and trusted quality communication	Strengthen trusted and modern brand image through digital and science-based communication	Maintain affordable accessibility and trusted essential baby care positioning	Strengthen trusted offline brand presence and retail visibility
Organization Capability	Improve organizational agility and faster decision-making responsiveness	Strengthen AI-driven consumer insight and digital responsiveness capability	Prioritize resource allocation for core products	Strengthen coordination between sales, operational, and retail execution teams

Implementation Roadmap

After establishing the implementation process, BabyM also requires an implementation roadmap which designed to support effective strategy execution, strengthen organizational readiness, and improve the company’s adaptability under future market uncertainty. Since future scenarios may continuously evolve and shift over time, the company requires a flexible capability development roadmap. Therefore, the roadmap is designed to strengthen long-term strategic capabilities that remain relevant across multiple future conditions while allowing implementation priorities and strategic emphasis to adapt according to changing market dynamics and dominant future scenarios. The implementation roadmap as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Implementation Roadmap (author’s analysis)

CONCLUSION

This study was conducted to strengthen BabyM's strategic foresight and sustain its market leadership in Indonesia's baby care industry amidst future uncertainty. Through Scenario Planning approach, this study explored possible future conditions that may influence BabyM's competitiveness over the next five years.

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